

Table 1 continued

Designation	Grain yield (t/ha)	% over ADT36 (local check)	Flowering duration (days)	Plant ht (cm)
Chianung Sen Yu 13	5.9	107.3	96	94
IR13540-56-3-2-1	7.8	141.8	91	75
RP825-45-1-3	6.2	112.7	100	84
<i>Check</i>				
IR36	3.0	54.5	95	82
BR10(BR51-46-5)	3.9	70.9	104	105
IR42	3.3	60.0	106	82
IR1552	1.4	25.5	98	83
ADT36 (local)	5.5	100.0	96	101
Mean (m)	4.2	76.4		
Std. deviation (σ)	1.2	21.8		
m + σ	5.4	98.2		

Table 2. Performance of promising entries from the 4th IRLRON, Tamil Nadu, India.

Designation	Grain yield (t/ha)	% of Pelita I-1 (local check)	Flowering duration (days)	Plant ht (cm)
<i>Entry</i>				
BR10(BR51-46-5)	4.8	123.1	99	113
IR13146-45-2	5.5	141.0	96	121
IR13505-30-B-3	4.8	123.1	89	86
IR4744-295-2-3	4.7	120.5	92	87
IR5873-9-1	5.0	128.2	89	106
IR9763-11-2-2-3	4.7	120.5	99	106
BIET927 (RAU 38-12-3-1)	4.5	115.4	123	146
BKN6990-63	5.0	128.2	119	157
BR111-140-1-1	4.5	115.4	114	148
CR1030	6.4	164.1	116	151
C424-2	4.5	115.4	106	124
IR13365-253-3-2	4.5	115.4	117	111
IR13564-109-1	4.7	120.5	116	100
IR14632-65-2	4.5	115.4	116	112
IR14875-98-5	4.5	115.4	113	104
IR19083-22-2-2	4.5	115.4	118	104
IR19431-72-2	5.4	138.5	103	94
IR3646-9-1-1	4.8	123.1	99	132
IR4819-77-3-2	5.4	138.5	106	133
IR4829-89-2	4.8	123.1	112	115
IR5857-64-IE-1-6	4.7	120.5	110	108
IR7545-27-3-2	4.7	120.5	106	100
IR9217-6-2-2-2-3	5.7	146.2	105	116
IR9763-11-2-2-3	4.5	115.4	106	109
KAU 2039	4.7	120.5	104	128
MR24	4.5	115.4	98	108
<i>Check</i>				
IR36	3.6	92.3	87	76
Cisadane	3.6	92.3	105	108
Mashuri	2.9	74.4	107	139
IR46	2.7	69.2	115	93
IR1552	1.6	41.0	105	75
IR20	2.9	74.4	98	127
Pelita I-1 (local)	3.9	100.0	103	114
Mean (m)	3.4	87.2		
Std. deviation (σ)	1.1	28.2		
m + σ	4.5	115.4		

The International Rice Research Newsletter (IRRN) invites all scientists to contribute concise summaries of significant rice research for publication. Contributions should be limited to one or two pages and no more than two short tables, figures, or photographs. Contributions are subject to editing and abridgement to meet space limitations. Authors will be identified by name, title, and research organization.

Heenati/IR30(BPHS)/IR2823-399-5) had the highest yield (7.8 t/ha in 121 days), 41.8% more than the local check (Table 1). Yields of 30 other entries and ADT36 ranged from 5.4 to 7.0 t/ha.

For IRLRON, CR1030 (Waikoku/CR 1014-211) had the highest yield (6.4 t/ha in 146 days), 64.1% more than the best check (Table 2). Yields of 24 other entries ranged from 4.5 to 5.5 t/ha.

The only insect observed during the season was whorl maggot, within a threshold level of 20%. There was no disease incidence. Based on grain yield and ancillary characters, 28 entries from IRON and 3 entries from IRLRON, all of medium duration, have been selected for further testing. ■

GENETIC EVALUATION AND UTILIZATION

Disease resistance

Resistance of rice cultivars to *Xanthomonas campestris* pv. *oryzae* at seedling and adult stages

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The clipping method was used to inoculate 20-day-old seedlings of 428 cultivars with a highly virulent isolate of *Xanthomonas campestris* pv. *oryzae*. Average lesion lengths of the seedling leaves were recorded 15 days after inoculation. Adult stage damage was rated on the standard evaluation scale for rice (0-4 resistant and 4.1-9 susceptible).

Thirteen cultivars showed resistance at both seedling and adult stages (see table). Cultivars carrying *Xa 1*, *Xa 2*, *Xa 3*, and *xa 5* were resistant at seedling as well as the adult stage. IR20 carrying the gene *Xa 4* was susceptible at both stages.

Some cultivars showed resistance at the seedling stage only — ARC 6172, ARC 6181, ARC 6615, ARC 7251, B-76, IR15529-26-1-1-2, IR15529-253-2-2-2, NCS-2003, NCS 2014, NCS 2039,

NCS 2041, NCS 2043, NCS 2044, NCS 2046, NCS 2048, NCS 2049, NCS 2055, NCS 2057, NCS 2072, NCS 2107, and Palman 579. Lesion lengths ranged from 2.2 cm to 3.6 cm. Some cultivars were susceptible as seedlings but resistant at adult stage — ARC 5913, ARC 5938, ARC 5951, ARC 6248, ARC 10602, ARC 11281, Denga Faram, IR2035-117-3, IR15705-199-3-3, Jhina, Jikkoku/Serpheke chil 52-102, Mudgo, NCS 320, NCS 332, NCS 338, NCS 335, NCS 2015, NCS 2018, Sinna Sivappu, T 1426, Vallathil Cheera, and Vellai Langayan. Disease scores ranged from 2.2 to 3.8. ■

Disease reaction of some rice stocks at seedling and at adult plant stage at Punjab, India.

Stock or cultivar	Source	Lesion length (cm) at seedling stage		Scores at adult stage (0-9 scale)
		Mean	Range	
MTU15/Waiseakokku-127	CRR1	3.65	2.0-7.0	2.7
ARC6044	CRR1	3.75	2.5-5.0	4.0
ARC11321	CRR1	3.68	2.0-6.0	3.4
ARC11367	CRR1	2.75	2.0-4.5	2.2
IET6123	CRR1	3.40	2.5-4.5	3.4
NCS2001	CRR1	3.50	1.5-5.0	3.0
NCS2009	CRR1	1.43	0.5-2.5	3.2
NCS2039	CRR1	2.48	2.0-3.5	3.7
NCS1604	CRR1	3.98	2.0-8.0	3.4
Kogyoku (<i>Xa 1</i>)	IRRI	1.50	1.0-2.0	0.8
Tetep (<i>Xa 1 + Xa 2</i>)	IRRI	1.20	0.5-2.5	1.4
Wau Qikoku-3 (<i>Xa 3</i>)	IRRI	2.23	1.0-4.5	1.7
IR1545-339 (<i>xa 5</i>)	IRRI	2.95	2.0-4.5	1.3
IR20 (<i>Xa 4</i>)	IRRI	4.78	3.0-7.0	5.6
TN1 (susceptible check)		16.68	8.5-26.5	6.5

Bacterial blight resistance under natural conditions

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During the 1980 and 1981 wet seasons, bacterial blight appeared in epidemic form in several pockets of the Chhatisgarh region. During the high natural infection in 1981, germplasm accessions of early and medium duration were screened for resistance, using the Standard Evaluation System for Rice scale.

Of 6,129 cultivars screened, only 1 scored 1, 24 scored 3, and the others 5-9

(Table 1). No seed could be harvested from several highly susceptible lines. No very early variety was resistant.

The 25 cultivars with scores of 1 and 3 (Table 2) have been selected for further tests under artificial inoculation. They have also been crossed with varieties carrying known resistance genes to study their allelic relationship. ■

Table 1. Resistance of germplasm accessions of rice of different maturities for natural bacterial blight epidemic in Raipur, M.P. India.

Maturity group	Accessions screened (no.)	Accessions (no.) with given bacterial blight resistance ^a score				
		1	3	5	7	9
Extra early (up to 90 days)	558	0	0	14	122	422
Very early (91 to 110 days)	496	0	3	57	138	298
Early (111 to 125 days)	2313	1	11	205	833	1263
Medium (126 to 140 days)	2762	0	10	744	1058	950
Total	6129	1	24	1020	2151	2933

^aStandard Evaluation System for Rice, % hills affected: 1 = less than 1%, 3 = 1-5%, 5 = 6-25%, 7 = 26-50%, 9 = 51-100%.

Table 2. Bacterial blight-resistant varieties at Raipur, M.P., India.

Karhani	Kechana
Benikath	Khuraban
Bhatapyagi	Liktimati
Badshahbhog	Ruingi
Bhatagunda	Rotad
Chingerchopa	Rageem 14
Chinee Kapoor	Safed jeera
Dilbaksa	Sataka
Gotaka	SLO
Jalkesar	Tikurdhan
Kesariya	Vishnubhog
Kosma	X 11
Kariyakora	

Varietal reaction to natural infection of rice tungro virus in Bihar

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Rice tungro virus infection under natural conditions was very high during 1980-81 kharif. The disease appeared the first week of August in transplanted Taichung Native 1 in a dryland field and

Table 1. Varietal reaction to rice tungro virus at Bihar, India.

Resistance score ^a	Released varieties	Promising varieties
3	Pusa 2-21, CR44-35 (Saket 4) Ratna, BR34, Janaki (64-117), BR9, Katarni, IR20	Pusa 33, TCA4, TCA177
5	Rajendra Dhan 201	TCA80-4, IET6263, RP1045-403-1
7	Rasi (IET1444), BR14, BR8, Type 3, Pankaj, Sita, PR106	BIET927, BIET1107, IET5656, ET5882, FH132
9	Jaya, IR8, Mahsuri, BR46, Prasad, Bala, Cauvery, NC1626, Improved Sona	UPR82-1-7, IET6155, BIET724, BG90-2, TCA62-68, TCA62-10, BIET1048, BIET821, IET2707, CRMS37, IET5883, IET5890, IET6314, IET5897, IET6212

^a1980 Standard Evaluation System for Rice scale of 0-9: 3 = 6-10% incidence, 9 = 81-100%.